

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of a dinuclear nickel complex : A bio-relevant catalyst and its reactivity

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Abstract : A new dinuclear nickel(II) complex, $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{L})(\mu\text{-CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ (**1**), of a (N,O)-donor Schiff base ligand ($\text{H}_2\text{L} = 2\text{-}((2\text{-hydroxyphenylimino)methyl)\text{-}6\text{-methoxyphenol}$), has been synthesized and isolated in crystalline phase. The nickel(II) complex has been characterized by elemental analysis, FTIR, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Powder X-ray diffraction study (PXRD), ESI mass spectrometry and thermogravimetric analysis. PXRD revealed that **1** crystallizes in P-1 space group with $a = 9.83572 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 9.86839 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 15.21101 \text{ \AA}$ with unit cell volume is $1471.136 (\text{ \AA})^3$. The nickel(II) complex displays significant catecholase oxidation activity in methanol medium. The interaction between the complex and calf thymus DNA (CT-DNA) has been investigated using spectrophotometric and spectrofluorimetric techniques, and it also been found to induce effective cleavage of the supercoiled pBR 322 DNA. The activity data show that the nickel(II) complex has effectively screened bacterial and fungal activity.

Keywords : Nickel(II), Schiff base, catecholase activity, DNA binding, DNA cleavage, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Structure and reactivity studies of nickel(II) complexes of (N,O)-donor ligands have been considered to be important in the bioinorganic chemistry owing to the biomimetic nature of such complexes in the context of metalloenzymes^{1,2}. In spite of the very rich coordination chemistry of nickel, its biological significance is not well developed. All types of nickel enzymes known to date are of plant or bacteria origins³⁻⁵. In the past few years, considerable interest has been grown in searching for small coordination molecules that exhibit enzymatic activity to mimic the structure as well as the functional properties of metalloenzymes^{6,7}.

Metal complexes that are able of binding and cleaving DNA hydrolytically (and selectively) would be highly desirable as they do not require any external agents and this gives valuable information to explore the potential chemotherapeutic agents⁸. Further, the sequence specific nature of the DNA cutting has been proved earlier that a binding event is central to scission mechanism⁹. This has resulted in the development of several artificial

metallonucleases which have potential applications as therapeutic agents and as a versatile replacement for nucleases as laboratory tools¹⁰⁻¹². However, there are only a few reports on the utilization of nickel complexes to cleave plasmid DNA¹³. In this present study, we report a design and synthesis of an octahedral dinuclear nickel(II) complex with a (N,O)-donor Schiff base ligand [$\text{H}_2\text{L} = 2\text{-}((2\text{-hydroxyphenylimino)methyl)\text{-}6\text{-methoxyphenol}$]. The bioactivity of the Ni^{II} complex has been investigated through catechol oxidation, CT-DNA binding studies, pBR 322 DNA cleavage activity and antimicrobial activity.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and solution properties of the Ni^{II} complex :

The complex **1** was prepared by treating nickel(II) acetate with the Schiff base ligand in 2 : 1 molar ratio in methanol as solvent. The complex **1** has been isolated as brown coloured crystalline compound. Based on elemental analysis and other fundamental spectroscopic techniques the complex **1** was formulated as $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{L})(\mu\text{-CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$. The complex was soluble in common

organic solvents such as MeOH, MeCN and DMSO. It was stable in the solid state as well as in the solution phase. The intense absorption band observed in the UV region (236 nm) is attributed to the intraligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the coordinated imine of the ligand origin. The high intensity band (310 nm), which is assignable to phenolate anion to Ni^{II} ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) transition, reveals the involvement of the phenolate oxygen atom in coordination even in solution. In order to probe the solution stability of the complexes, we have performed UV-Vis spectral measurements for methanolic solution of the complexes at room temperature at various time intervals. Low intensity and broad transitions at 376 and 424 nm are attributed to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively in Ni^{II} octahedral field (Fig. S2)¹⁴ and these bands remained unaffected over a period of at least 5 days revealing that the complexes are stable in solution at room temperature.

Spectroscopic characterization :

In IR spectrum of **1** the well resolved peak at 3398 cm⁻¹ is attributed to aliphatic $\nu(\text{O-H})$ and the peaks at 1621, 1605 cm⁻¹ are due to $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (Fig. S1). The characteristic symmetrical bifurcated peaks of **1** at 1475, 1434 cm⁻¹ is attributed to $\nu(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)$ for bridging carboxylate moieties and the well resolved peaks in the region 1249 to 1181 cm⁻¹ assigns the methoxo-coordination to nickel(II) center¹⁵. The compound shows weak bands in the range 2980–2900 cm⁻¹ are assignable to the aliphatic C-H stretching frequency.

The mass spectral study of Ni^{II} complex in acetonitrile medium is in good agreement with the theoretical molecular mass of the complexes and also the data confirm the dinuclear nature of the Ni^{II} complex. The ESI mass spectrum (Fig. S3) of **1** shows the base peak as most abundant peak at 545.84 (Calcd. 545.86), which is assigned as the molecular ion peak of **1**. ESI-MS (MeCN) m/z 545.84 $[[\text{Ni}_2(\text{L})(\mu\text{-CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3] + \text{H}]^+$ (Calcd. 545.86).

PXRD characterization :

The powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{L})(\mu\text{-CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ is shown in Fig. 2. All the peaks in the diffraction pattern can be indexed with the triclinic structure with P-1 space group using WINPLOTR programme. The extracting cell parameters are $a = 9.83572 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 9.86839 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 15.21101 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 91.94374^\circ$, $\beta = 94.21336^\circ$, $\gamma = 91.26832^\circ$ and the unit cell volume is 1471.136 (\AA^3). From PXRD, it is revealed that the complex is in pure crystalline phase.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The thermal behaviour of the nickel(II) complex was followed up to 800 °C in a static nitrogen atmosphere with a heating rate of 10 °C per minute. $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{L})(\mu\text{-CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ (**1**) decomposed in three steps (Fig. S4). In the first step from 30 to 107 °C corresponds to the endothermic process with the loss of coordinated aqua molecules with the mass loss of 9.97% (Calcd. 9.91%)

Fig. S1. IR spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex (**1**).

Fig. S2. UV-Vis spectrum of the complex (1).

Fig. S3. Thermogravimetric analysis spectrum of the complex (1).

and the experimental mass loss agrees excellent with calculated mass loss. In the second and third steps from 107 to 399 °C, there is loss of two coordinated bridging acetate molecules and the coordination environment around the nickel centers.

Kinetics of the oxidation of 3,5-di-tert-butylcatechol :

Catechol oxidases are type III copper proteins which catalyze the oxidation of catechols to quinones in the presence of oxygen¹⁶. The catecholase activity of complex **1** was studied using 3,5-DTBC as a convenient model substrate, in air saturated methanol solvent at room temperature (25 °C). For this purpose, a 1×10^{-4} M solution of this complex was treated with 1×10^{-2} M (100 equiv.) of 3,5-DTBC and the course of the reaction was followed by recording the UV-Vis spectra of the mixture at an interval of 5 min for 2 h. Spectral bands at 236, 310, 376 and 424 nm appeared in the electronic spectrum of complex **1** in methanol, whereas 3,5-DTBC showed a single band at 284 nm. As the reaction proceeded, there was a gradual decrease in intensity of the band at 284 nm due to the catechol¹⁷ and an initial new band was formed at ~408 nm (Fig. 3), which indicated the formation of the respective quinone derivative and the band maximum is gradually shifted to 404 nm. 3,5-DTBQ, which was purified by column chromatography and isolated in high yield (76.2% for **1**) by slow evaporation of the eluant. The product was identified by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. ¹H NMR

Fig. S4. Mass spectrum of the nickel(II) complex (1).

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of the dinuclear nickel(II) complex (1).

Fig. 2. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns along with h, k, l values for Ni^{II} complex (1).

Fig. 3. Increase of quinone band at 404 nm after addition of 100 equivalents of (3,5-DTBC) to a solution containing complex (1) (10^{-4} M) in methanol at 25 °C. The spectra were recorded after every 5 min.

(CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ_{H} : 1.16 (9H, s), 1.20 (9H, s), 6.15 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 6.86 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz).

The kinetics of oxidation of 3,5-DTBC were determined by the method of initial rates and involved monitoring the growth of the quinone band at 404 nm as a function of time¹⁸. The colour of the solution gradually turned deep brown, indicative of the gradual conversion of 3,5-DTBC to 3,5-DTBQ. The difference in absorbance ΔA at 404 nm was plotted against time to obtain the rate for that particular catalyst to substrate concentration ratio (Fig. 4). A first-order catalytic reaction was observed, with the rate $2.49 \times 10^{-5} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for 1.

Fig. 4. A plot of the difference in absorbance (ΔA) vs time to evaluate the velocity of the catalysis by the complex (1).

Mechanistic pathway interpretation for catechol oxidation :

Detailed investigations with copper-based model complexes of catechol oxidase have shown that various factors may affect their catalytic activity, such as the metal-metal distance, the flexibility of the ligand, the type of exogenous bridging ligand, and the coordination geometry around the metal center¹⁹. Very detailed studies on the substrate binding to the copper(II) complexes with the phenol-based dinucleating ligands were also reported by Belle *et al.*²⁰. Another detailed investigation on catechol oxidation by dinuclear nickel complex with a phenol based Schiff base ligand has been reported by Ghosh *et al.*²¹. The oxidation of catechol to the corresponding quinone is a two electron process; therefore, it requires two metal centers that will shuttle between the +2 and +1 states. In our dinuclear nickel(II) molecule, the presence of labile

groups at each of the nickel(II) center makes easy to bind the substrate (3,5-DTBC) and follows the mechanistic pathway presented by Belle *et al.*

Fluorescence spectral studies :

Ethidium bromide (EB) is chemically known as 3,8-diamino-5-ethyl-6-phenylphenanthridinium bromide. It is

Scheme 1. Mechanistic pathway for the oxidation of catechol by dinuclear nickel(II) complex (L = Schiff base ligand coordinated to nickel centers are omitted for clarity).

DNA binding studies :

Electronic absorption titration :

Electronic absorption spectroscopy is an effective method to determine the binding mode of metal complex with DNA. To examine the binding mode of dinuclear nickel(II) complex with DNA, the absorption spectra of complex, was recorded during the titration with CT-DNA. As shown in Fig. 5, the spectra indicate a significant hyperchromism effect centered at 272 nm absorption maximum which suggests that the complex interact with CT-DNA through a groove binding. In general, the observation of hyperchromism is associated with the binding of the metal complex to DNA helix, due to the groove binding mode involving a strong hydrogen bonding interaction between the complex and the base pairs of DNA²². The binding constants, K_b for the complex has been determined from the plot of $[DNA]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ vs $[DNA]$ and found to be $7.5(\pm 0.2) \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9909$ for five points) (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Electronic absorption spectra of nickel complex through titration with CT-DNA in tris-HCl buffer. The increase of DNA concentration is indicated by an arrow. [Inset : Linear plot of $[DNA]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ vs $[DNA]$ for the titration of CT-DNA with the complex in tris-HCl buffer, binding constant, $K_b = 7.5(\pm 0.2) \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9909$ for five points)].

a large, flat molecule that resembles a DNA base pair. EB can emit intense fluorescence in presence of DNA due to the strong intercalation between the adjacent DNA base pairs. The fluorescent light of EB-DNA system can be quenched by addition of the second agent, since it interacts with DNA. The quenching degree of fluorescence for EB-DNA system is usually used to determine the binding extent of the agent and DNA²³. The addition of the Ni complex to DNA pretreated with EB causes an appreciable reduction in the fluorescence intensity (Fig. 6). The reduction of the emission intensity gives a measure of the DNA binding propensity of the complex. Here, for the nickel complex, a significant decrease of the fluorescence intensity of EB bound to DNA at 620–

DNA cleavage activity :

Incubation of the complex **1** with the pBR 322 DNA resulted in the cleavage of the DNA (Fig. 7). The cleavage of the DNA was confirmed by the appearance of the band when compared with the control DNA. With the increasing of the concentration of the complex (25, 50, 75 and 100 μg) the cleavage of the supercoiled pBR 322 DNA was clearly observed with the changes in the band size. 100 μg of the sample resulted in complete disappearance of the band.

Bio-activity :

In testing the antibacterial and antifungal activity of these compounds, we used more than one test organism

Fig. 6. Left : Emission spectra of the CT-DNA-EB system in tris-HCl buffer based on the titration of the complex. The arrow indicates the increase of the complex concentration. Right : Plot of I_0/I vs [complex] for the titration of CT-DNA-EB system with the complex using spectrofluorimeter; linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant, $K_{sv} = 2.4 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$; ($R = 0.9917$ for five points).

628 nm were recorded by increasing the concentration of the complex (Fig. 6). The quenching of EB bound to DNA by the nickel(II) complex is in agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation :

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{sv} [\text{complex}]$$

where I_0 and I represent the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively. K_{sv} is the linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant and [complex] the concentration of the quencher. From the slope of the regression line in the derived plot of I_0/I versus [complex] (Fig. 6), the K_{sv} value for the complex was found to be $2.5 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$; ($R = 0.9917$ for five points), indicating a strong affinity of the nickel complex to CT-DNA.

Fig. 7. Concentration dependent cleavage of the supercoiled pBR 322 DNA by the Ni-complex (**1**). Lane 1 shows the control DNA. Lanes 2–5 show DNA + complex (25, 50, 75 and 100 μg , respectively).

to increase the chance of detecting antibiotic principles in tested materials. 100 μL of microbial suspension was spread onto agar plates corresponding to the broth in

which they were maintained. Isolated colonies of each organism that might be playing a pathogenic role should be selected from primary agar plates and tested for susceptibility by well diffusion method. The metal complex has been screened for their antimicrobial activity (Fig. S5) and the results are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

Fig. S5. Antibacterial effect of the complex (1).

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of the complex (Well size : 6 mm) at different concentrations

Organisms	10 μ g	20 μ g	30 μ g	50 μ g
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	–	2 mm	3 mm	4 mm
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	–	–	1 mm	2 mm
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	6 mm	7 mm	8 mm	11 mm
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	3 mm	5 mm	6 mm	7 mm
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	–	–	–	2 mm

Table 2. Antifungal activity of the complex (Well size : 6 mm) at different concentrations

Organisms	10 μ g	20 μ g	30 μ g	50 μ g
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	2 mm	3 mm	4 mm	6 mm
<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	–	–	3 mm	4 mm
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	–	–	1 mm	2 mm

In our case, metal-ligand coordination reduces the polarity of the metal ion significantly which makes this dinuclear Ni^{II} complex non-polar and it is also reflected from the solubility of this complex in various non-polar solvents. This non-polar character in this Ni^{II} complex, it is probably adsorbed on the surface of the cell wall of microorganisms and disturbs the respiration process of the cell and thus blocks the synthesis of the proteins that

restricts further growth of the organisms. So, the Ni^{II} complex behaves as the growth-inhibitor for microorganism.

Conclusion

A new dinuclear nickel(II) complex with a (N,O)-donor Schiff base ligand has been synthesized and isolated in crystalline phase. Structural, spectroscopic and solution properties of the compound have also been investigated. The neutral binuclear Ni^{II} complex shows significant catalytic influence on the oxidation of 3,5-DTBC to the corresponding *o*-quinones. The Ni^{II} complex exhibits profound cleavage to pBR 322 DNA at different concentration. The biological activities of the Ni^{II} complex against bacterial and fungal organisms are quite promising which need further investigations on animals and humans.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity *o*-vanilin (E. Merck, India), *o*-aminophenol (E. Merck, India), nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate and all other solvents were purchased from the respective concerns and used as received. 3,5-Di-tert-butylcatechol (3,5-DTBC) was obtained from Sigma Aldrich Corporation (St. Louis, MO, USA). All other chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade and were used as received without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–300 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX1 spectrometer. Ground-state absorption measurements were made with a Jasco model V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The crystalline phase was identified by powder X-ray diffraction patterns (XRD) of the materials by using a BRUKER AXS (Model : 8D-ADVANCE) diffractometer with a Cu K α radiation source under continuous scanning mode in the range 8–60°. Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectrum was recorded using a Q-tof-micro quadrupole mass spectrometer.

Preparation of H₂L and nickel complex 1 :

The Schiff base H₂L was prepared following a re-

ported method²⁴. To prepare the Schiff base ligand, *o*-aminophenol (0.1092 g, 1 mmol) was refluxed with *o*-vanillin (0.1523 g, 1 mmol) in 20 ml dehydrated alcohol and red coloured crystalline compound was isolated from solution, which was dried and stored *in vacuo* over CaCl₂ for subsequent use.

Scheme 2. Structure of the ligand.

A methanolic solution (5 cm³) of H₂L (0.244 g, 1 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of Ni(OAc)₂·4H₂O (0.496 g, 2 mmol) in the same solvent (10 cm³). The red solution of the ligand turned into brown and after filter the supernatant liquid was kept in air for slow evaporation.

Yield : 0.342 g (69% based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₅NO₁₀Ni₂ (**1**) : C, 41.89; H, 4.63; N, 2.57. Found : C, 41.80; H, 4.57; N, 2.64%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3398 (ν_{OH}), 1621, 1605 (ν_{C=N}), 1475, 1434 (ν_{OAc})_{sym}; UV-Vis (λ_{max}, nm) : 236, 310, 376, 424.

Catalytic oxidation of 3,5-DTBC :

In order to examine the catecholase activity of the complex, a 10⁻⁴ M solution of **1** in methanol solvent was treated with 100 equiv. of 3,5-di-tert-butylcatechol (3,5-DTBC) under aerobic conditions at room temperature. Absorbance vs wavelength (wavelength scans) of these solutions were recorded at a regular time interval of 5 min in the wavelength range 300–500 nm. To determine the dependence of rate on substrate concentration and various kinetic parameters, a 10⁻⁴ M solution of the complex was treated with at least 10 equiv. of substrate so as to maintain the pseudo-first order condition. The reaction was followed spectrophotometrically by monitoring the increase in the absorbance at 404 nm (Quinone band maxima) as a function of time (time scan).

DNA binding experiments :

All experiments involving CT-DNA were performed

in tris-HCl buffer solution. Stock solution of DNA was stored at 4 °C. The buffer solution of CT-DNA gave a ratio value of UV absorbance at 260 and 280 nm of about 1.9, indicating that the DNA was sufficiently independent of protein²⁵. The concentration CT-DNA per nucleotide was determined by UV absorption spectroscopy using the absorption coefficient (6600 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) at 260 nm²⁶. The solution of complex **1** was prepared by dissolving the complex in dimethyl formamide and diluted suitably with tris-HCl buffer (5 mM tris(hydroxyl methyl)aminomethane, tris, pH 7.2, 50 mM NaCl) to required concentrations for all the experiments. Absorption spectra were recorded after each successive addition of DNA and equilibration (approximately 10 min). From the observed data, the intrinsic binding constant, K_b was calculated by using the following equation²⁷.

$$[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f) = [\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f) + 1/K_b(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$$

where ε_a, ε_f, ε_b are the apparent, free and bound compound extinction coefficients. A plot of [DNA]/(ε_b - ε_f) versus [DNA] gave a slope of 1/(ε_b - ε_f) and a 'y' intercept equal to 1/K_b(ε_b - ε_f), where K_b is the ratio of the slope to the y intercept.

Ethidium bromide (EB) fluorescence displacement experiments were also performed in order to investigate the interaction mode of the nickel complex with CT-DNA. EB has been used to probe the interaction of the complexes with DNA. In fact the EB fluorescence intensity will be enhanced in the presence of DNA because of its intercalation into the helix, and it is quenched by the addition of another molecule that displaces EB from DNA²⁸. Here, a significant decrease of the fluorescence intensity of EB bound to DNA at 620–628 nm was recorded by increasing the concentration of complex. The quenching of EB bound to DNA by the complex is in agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation :

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{sv} [\text{complex}]$$

where I₀ and I represent the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively. K_{sv} is the linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant and [complex] the concentration of the quencher.

DNA cleavage studies :

Cleavage of supercoiled pBR 322 DNA by **1** was

monitored by agarose gel electrophoresis technique. The complexes (25–100 µg) were incubated with pBR 322 DNA overnight at 37 °C. After incubation 2 µL of bromophenol blue dye was mixed with the sample and loaded carefully into the electrophoresis chamber wells along with the control DNA. TAE buffer was used as a running buffer and finally loaded on agarose gel and passed the constant 50 V of electricity for 50 min. Then the bands were observed in the gel containing EB under the gel documentation system and photographed to determine the extent of DNA cleavage and the results are compared with the control.

In vitro antimicrobial activity :

Antibacterial activity of the complex was tested against the bacterial species *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* by well diffusion method²⁹. The complex was also tested against the fungal species *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Aspergillus niger* cultured on sabouraud dextrose agar medium by the well diffusion method. The bacteria test organisms were grown on muller hinton agar and the fungal species on sabouraud dextrose agar in petri plates. The pathogens were swabbed uniformly onto the individual plates using sterile cotton swabs. Using gel puncture, wells of 6 mm diameter were made. Different concentration (25 µg, 50 µg, 75 µg and 100 µg) of test sample was poured onto each well on all plates. After incubation at 37 °C for 24 h for bacteria and 28 °C for 72 h for fungi, the different levels of zone of inhibition were measured.

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